

stunt disease may not be entirely due to BPH resistance; the rice variety Gangala is also resistant to the three known BPH biotypes, but it had a high percentage of seedlings infected with ragged stunt disease in the same inoculation test (see

table). Hence, Ptb 21 Acc. no. 11053 may be resistant not only to BPH but also to ragged stunt disease.

Experiments to confirm this finding are under way.

Occurrence of water mold disease of rice seed and seedlings in Bangladesh

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A disease that caused rice seeds and seedlings to rot was found in seedbeds of the boro season this year. The causal organism is a phycomycetous fungus of the genus *Achlya*, commonly known as water mold. The species, which has not yet been identified, attacks sprouting

seeds and affects germination. Even if a seed germinates, the seedling soon rots or its vigor is reduced.

A few days after infection, a brownish, cottony, hyphal growth was found around the seeds. The disease was severe when the seedbed was submerged for 3 to 4 days during seedling emergence or after the sowing of sprouted seeds. Cold weather seems to have aggravated the situation. About 10 to 50% of the seed and seedlings either rotted or showed damping-off. Dry seedbeds did not have the disease.

A preliminary survey of seedbeds on the BRRI farm indicated that rice varieties differ markedly in susceptibility to the disease at one of the two stages (see table). Highly susceptible varieties were BR3, BR6, BR7, Hashikalmi, and Habiganj Boro II, IV, and VIII.

This is the first report of the occurrence of such a disease in Bangladesh. To prevent seedling loss due to this disease, seedbed submergence should be avoided.

Evaluation for sheath blight resistance in rice

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From 1975 to 1977, efforts were made at the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project to develop simple, rapid, and mass inoculation methods to induce sheath blight disease in rice and to evaluate germplasm and breeding lines in the field and in glasshouses. Preliminary results are reported elsewhere; this article reports screening methodology and catalogues entries that showed sheath blight tolerance in fields and glasshouses.

The pathogen *Rhizoctonia solani* was isolated from affected leaves and sheaths collected from farmers' fields in a sheath blight-endemic region of West Godavari district, A.P. The pathogen was multiplied on shoots of the water sedge *Typha angustata*. *Typha* shoots are preferred to rice stem pieces because *Typha* stems are strong enough to withstand mechanical handling when inoculated and are readily available the year-round in irrigation and drainage channels. *Typha* shoots measuring 7.6 to 10.2 cm (3–4 in.) in length were soaked in 1% peptone water in 1-liter Erlenmeyer flasks for 7 days. The shoot pieces having mycelium and sclerotia were placed between the tillers in the central region of the rice hills, 5 to 10 cm above the waterline.

The field layout for screening included a normal 2-row observational nursery with

Reaction of some boro varieties and lines to water mold disease of rice at the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute farm.

Cultivar	Disease incidence (%)		Cultivar	Disease incidence (\$6)	
	Rotten seeds	Affected seedlings		Rotten seeds	Affected seedlings
BG 902	9.5	26.7	IR747-B2-6-3	3.6	68.9
BR 3	39.7	29.5	IR910-12-3-1-3	11.6	10.9
BR 6	4.2	40.9	IR944-85-1-2-1-1-2-1	19.1	6.4
BR 7	52.1	16.7	IR1103-15-8	38.6	42.5
BR 20-29-2	5.00	11.5	IR1514-E666	4.5	48.9
BR 43-11-2	1.00	3.8	IR1529-430-3	5.6	12.2
BR 43-11-3	0.0	0.0	IR2003-P17-7-4-2	18.9	32.2
BR 52-315-12	0.0	4.0	IR2031-724-2-3-2	47.00	41.8
BR 167-2B-3	4.0	15.1	IR2035-117-3	1.9	18.5
BR 167-2B-9	28.5	37.2	IR2038-158-2-3	3.3	16.2
BR 167-26-2-1	27.2	12.3	IR2053-87-3-1	20.8	16.8
Chandina	25.9	47.1	IR2053-160-3	90.0	8.0
Chandina/HR29-4	0.0	0.0	IR205 3-200-4	90.0	8.0
Chandrosail I	31.4	7.6	IR2053-362-1-4-4	95.0	3.0
CR 120	90.00	8.0	IR2061-214-3-3-28	5.9	5.1
Habiganj BoroII	3.9	16.9	IR2061-214-3-3-32	4.4	1.8
Habiganj Boro IV	8.00	18.4	IR2061-423-1	16.8	19.0
Habiganj Boro VI	3.3	15.1	IR2061-465-1-5	7.1	10.0
Habiganj Boro VIII	17.5	22.6	IR2061-628-1-1-1-4-3	16.7	46.3
Hashikalmi	29.00	6.0	IR2070-423-2-5-6	1.1	22.9
IET 1444	4.6	29.9	IR2070-414-3-9	5.7	56.2
IET 2845	5.7	8.9	IR2071-625-1-252	6.5	8.9
IET 2895	0.0	0.0	IR2871-53-2	3.1	29.7
IR8	11.6	11.2	IR3403-267-1	9.1	45.5
IR20	95.0	3.0	IR4405-451	8.9	35.2
IR28	7.6	10.3	Mala/Comilla	3.1	6.4
IR29	6.6	11.0	Mala/Habiganj	4.8	7.6
IR32	8.5	12.2	Mala/J15	0.0	0.0
IR78-177-3-2-2	12.00	5.2	Ratna	1.0	5.2
IR382-4-3-2	7.5	7.5	TN1	3.0	2.0